

Visual Exchanges as a Network: The Case of Avant-Garde Periodicals

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In the history of representation, the illustrated press has functioned as a significant driving force, curating and disseminating ideas of visuality to artists and a wider audience. An illustration published in one magazine could be shared or copied by another, while periodical editors absorbed ideas from different publications and reused them in novel settings. The result is a network of exchanges, a polycentric map that shows how the visual spreads across space, time, and the public sphere. However, how can we even capture the interaction and circulation of the visual at scale? How is it possible to analyse and comprehend image globalization? To answer these questions, the Visual Contagions project³⁴ has developed a global corpus comprising more than 4000 illustrated magazines from 1890 to 1990. Using computer vision algorithms³⁵, we extracted more than 10 million images from their pages, compared them together and arranged them into clusters of "image types": vectors of visually similar images. In parallel, for each retrieved publication, and thus for each image extracted, we collected and normalised a set of descriptors documenting the date and place of publication, as well as the type of audience (community type) to which each periodical was addressed (e.g. Avant-garde Art, Automobile, Male Fashion).

By combining the two data sources, we were able to query each image type and analyse the spatiotemporal attributes of its component, i.e. where each identified image was published, by which periodical, for which audience and on which date. The result is an initial panorama of globalisation through images, which reveal unexpected axes of circulation between countries. However, if such work has shed light on the geographical and thematic distribution of exchanges, it has not yet explained the process of visual dissemination and image distribution.

Following the example of previous investigations³⁶, this contribution applies network science methods and metrics to the study of the exchanges. Visual dissemination will be examined by focusing not on the entire Visual Contagions corpus, but on a specific case study: image exchanges within avant-garde magazines between 1910 and 1945 and their impact beyond the original community of readers.

The paper presents the process of selection and construction of a metadata network³⁷ and outlines the conceptual decisions behind it. The use of a centrality algorithm combined with a temporal analysis will make it possible to analyse the dynamic relationships between periodicals in the community and their role in image distribution at a national or international level. The analysis of these results will reveal which periodical was more active within the avant-garde community in incorporating visual inputs, as well as the role and tendency of national visual exchange in the art world.

This initial analysis focuses on the network of avant-garde magazines itself, and it reveals the dynamics of its structure and characteristics over time. However, in order to comprehend exchange, it is also important

³⁴ B. Joyeux-Prunel *et al.*, "Un œil mondial? La mondialisation par l'image au prisme du numérique: le cas du projet Visual Contagions," *Sociétés & Représentations*, vol. 75, no. 1, pp. 203-226, 2023

³⁵ R. Champenois and B. Joyeux-Prunel, "Visual Contagions : extraction et traitement d'images pour l'étude globale de la circulation d'images illustrées," *Humanistica* 2023, 2023

³⁶ E. Erikson and P. Bearman, "Malfeasance and the Foundations for Global Trade: The Structure of English Trade in the East Indies, 1601–1833," *American Journal of Sociology*, vol. 112, No. 1, pp. 195-230, 2006

³⁷ M. Grandjean, "Using Network Analysis to Question the Concepts of Centrality and Periphery in Complex Historical Structures," vol. Cultural Organizations: Between the Local and the Global, no. 1880s-1960s, 2020

to understand how the images produced within this network are received outside of it. For such an analysis, a network comprising all the magazines (and the publication/exchange data) documented in the Visual Contagions data will be created. Thus, the images produced by avant-garde magazines will be examined with respect to their impact on other non-avant-garde magazines and communities of readers. Specifically, we will examine how the images produced by avant-garde magazines are received outside the art community, which communities act as a bridge between avant-garde periodicals and non-art magazines (betweenness), and which avant-garde periodicals are more successful in distributing images outside (shortest path) their domain and community of readers.

This second investigation will reveal the extent of influence exerted by avant-garde magazines and identify the channels and communities through which they achieved cultural significance.